

Holistic Approach for Providing Spatial & Transport Planning Tools and Evidence to Metropolitan and Regional Authorities to Lead a Sustainable Transition to a New Mobility Era

D10.2 Communication kit

Expected submission date: 30/09/2019

[@Harmony_H2020](https://twitter.com/Harmony_H2020)

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<https://www.linkedin.com/company/harmony-h2020/>

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Part of:

SUMMARY SHEET

PROJECT

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Explanation
DEIC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Innovation Committee
H2020	Horizon 2020
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

HARMONY is providing public authorities of metropolitan areas with the right spatial and transport planning tools to lead a sustainable transition towards a new mobility era.

The objective of WP10 “Dissemination, Exploitation & Innovation Management” is to spread knowledge and information about the project research and innovation outcomes and results.

This document outlines HARMONY Communication kit supporting all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The general aim of the kit is to communicate the project plainly and effectively to all potential audiences. The Communication kit will be updated throughout the lifetime of the project according to the changing needs of the dissemination and communication activities, thus representing a useful tool for the whole consortium.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

Nowadays, new mobility services and technologies present a possible solution to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption in metropolitan areas. However, authorities face several challenges when it comes to harmoniously integrating these developments into spatial and transport plans to improve citizens' wellbeing and achieve environmental targets. Given rapid technological advances, emergence of new mobility services and changing urban sprawl, metropolitan authorities often lack sufficient expertise, knowledge and tools for multiscale spatial and transport planning.

Against this background, HARMONY's vision is to enable metropolitan area authorities to lead a sustainable transition to a low-carbon new mobility era. This will be possible thanks to its harmonised spatial and multimodal transport planning tools which comprehensively model the dynamics of the changing transport sector and spatial organisation.

HARMONY has set ambitious targets for the creation of updated spatial and transport planning tools. The consortium's intention is to widely disseminate the existence of the project goals and results not only within Europe but also internationally, in order to highlight Europe as a major force worldwide in the relevant scientific and industrial fields.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The objective of WP10 "Dissemination, Exploitation & Innovation Management" is to effectively spread knowledge and information about the project research and innovation outcomes and results in order to assist EU metropolitan areas in sustainable development and contribute to the H2020 agenda for smart, green and integrated mobility.

As part of this WP, this document outlines the Communication kit describing the communication material and tools. It will be updated throughout the project, according to the project needs and communication planning. This deliverable completes D10.1 Dissemination and communication strategy and plan by providing the project identity and creating consistency among the tools used by all partners.

1.3 Intended audience

The Communication kit is a public deliverable, i.e. it provides the communication material for the consortium partners to promote HARMONY among targeted stakeholders and general public. In addition, this deliverable will be available on the HARMONY website.

1.4 Structure of the document

This document consists of one main section describing the communication material, whose thumbnails will be shown in the Annex.

2. Communication kit

This section describes the communication material supporting HARMONY dissemination and communication activities. Each tool is part of a dissemination and communication channel, as described in HARMONY deliverable D10.1.

2.1 HARMONY brand identity

To give HARMONY a common image towards the outside world and to communicate it in a consistent way with a clear and recognisable brand, a project logo and an overall background have been created. A Microsoft Word and PowerPoint template using the HARMONY project identity have also been created, which will be used by all members of the consortium for presentations, written deliverables, etc.

2.2 Roll-up

In order to establish the visibility of HARMONY at major conferences, exhibitions and public meetings, the roll-up banner will provide information such as HARMONY's general idea, objectives, expected impact and the cities and regions, as well as the partners, the main contact points, the website and the social media.

2.3 Leaflet

The general idea of the leaflet is to present the project briefly and in a comprehensible way so as to inform the targeted audiences about HARMONY. The leaflet is constantly updated according to the project needs, so as to include new pictures and elements which resulted from the project's evolution. The first version has already been uploaded on the online repository.

The leaflet includes the vision and mission of the project, its objectives and expected results, as well as the contacts promoting HARMONY website and social media.

The leaflet will be printed and distributed by all project partners in their daily interactions with clients and other projects, as well as during events and workshops.

2.4 General presentation

The general project presentation is an electronic presentation consisting of few slides introducing the main project idea, objectives and expected results. This presentation will be used by all partners and to present and promote HARMONY. It will be adapted according to the audience and progressively updated to include the project's achievements. A PowerPoint template using the HARMONY project identity has also been created and stored in the online repository.

2.5 Website

The project website (<http://www.harmony-h2020.eu>) is the major channel for visibility of the HARMONY project: it describes the project and its aims at highlights its results to be achieved. The website content will be kept simple and straightforward so as to reach non-technical audiences with details on the project vision, concept, objectives, expected impact, proposed technologies, consortium members, cities and regions. It provides a place to share public deliverables, updates on the current research phases and results, present further developments and inform about upcoming events.

The website also serves as an interactive tool for internal and external communication. On the one hand, partners are expected to contribute with relevant information related to HARMONY activities and outcomes. This information shall be sent to the WP10 leader, who will check the appropriateness of the content for publication on the website. If necessary, the WP10 leader could contact the DEIC before publishing. On the other hand, visitors will find information about latest project developments, public past and future events related to HARMONY and the list of all the partners involved, thus reinforcing

the image and representativeness of the project. The goal is to make the website an actual source of information and contact point for further collaboration.

Therefore, the website will be the key stone to build HARMONY's internet community. It will provide a common approach for all HARMONY's material. It will represent an essential resource disseminating information about the project, facilitating collaboration amongst partners, and bringing together a diverse and scattered community.

2.6 Newsletter

The periodic newsletters, due every 6 months starting from November 2019, will summarize the project's activities and outcomes and proactively initiate conversations with multiple stakeholders about on-going research topics. The mailing list will be constantly updated to include all the people signing up on HARMONY website, where all published newsletter will be uploaded. Please check Annex VI of D10.1 for additional information about data privacy concerning newsletter and mailing lists management.

2.7 Social media

Several social media accounts have been activated for HARMONY:

- Twitter (@Harmony_H2020): to be especially used during specific conferences and workshops, promoting a dedicated hashtag assigned by the conference/workshop organizer.
- LinkedIn (Harmony-H2020, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/harmony-h2020>): will be used to create interest among experts on focused discussions and to post blogs and newsfeeds. Unlike private groups, HARMONY public profile is meant at targeting all LinkedIn users. A private group could be created, should the necessity arise in the future.
- YouTube (Harmony-H2020): a YouTube channel will be exploited as repository of promotional videos as well as a tool attracting the YouTube users.

Social media activities will assist partners to identify and invite interested experts to join the HARMONY End Users' Group. Furthermore, the consortium members will make use of their companies'/organisations' individual social networking profiles to diffuse project messages and discuss project innovations and proposed solutions with their contacts. HARMONY consortium will also seek every opportunity to diffuse project achievements through the H2020 and CIVITAS related social media accounts.

2.8 Press release

Press releases are intended to communicate the project's developments or announce important achievements. A press release is usually a one-page note presenting the message briefly, using simple language. They will be released periodically to inform about HARMONY's outputs and upcoming events.

WP leaders are especially requested to produce press releases on the results achieved. Nevertheless, all project members are expected to contribute to the dissemination of project results through the diffusion to local and national press in their respective countries. In addition, some details should be given by the partner in charge: source, publication date, target audience.

2.9 Videos

Videos will communicate HARMONY in an easy and engaging way. The videos will be available on the project's website and social media, as well as on other available channels and platforms, such as YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCi_JjN2qBy52x1Nb2NnyLEg). The videos will be also displayed in relevant events and conferences which HARMONY will organise or participate in.

3. Conclusions

This document presented HARMONY communication kit supporting all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The general aim of the kit is to communicate the project, its activities and results in an effective way and make the results and deliverables of the project available on a comprehensible manner to all the potential audiences. The communication kit will be updated throughout the project, according to the changing needs of the dissemination and communication activities.

References

HARMONY D10.1 Dissemination and communication strategy and plan, 2019.

HARMONY Grant Agreement, 2019.

ANNEX

HARMONY brand identity

Figure 1 - HARMONY logo

Figure 2 - HARMONY logo and title

Figure 3 - HARMONY logo, title and subtitle

Figure 4 - HARMONY background

HARMONY roll-up

HARMONY
REGIONAL & TRANSPORT PLANNING FOR A NEW MOBILITY ERA

Our mission

- Integration of new & traditional services for urban & regional passenger & freight mobility
- Engagement & demonstration
- Transport & Spatial Data Warehouse
- Integrated planning tools
- Recommendations for spatial & transport strategies

Our solutions

Model suite

It is a regional spatial and transport planning tool consisting of land-use, activity-based travel demand and traffic simulation models. It will forecast the multi-dimensional impact of disruptive mobility services, technologies and concepts. Integration with an EU-wide model will allow for scale-up and further impact quantification on a TEN-T level.

Training

Authorities and transport professionals will develop skills and knowledge to use the model suite tools. They will also provide advice for future projects and exploitation activities.

Best practices for SUMP

The best practices for SUMP will provide authorities with evidence-based recommendations to update their Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, including autonomous vehicles and drones.

Our team

21 partners from 9 European countries

www.harmony-h2020.eu
 Harmony-H2020
 Harmony_H2020

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 Part of 2020-2023

Figure 5 - HARMONY roll-up

HARMONY leaflet

New spatial & transport **planning tools** to enable
a sustainable transition to a **new mobility era**

Figure 6 - HARMONY leaflet front

Our mission

- Integration of new & traditional services for urban & regional passenger & freight mobility
- Engagement & demonstration
- Transport & Spatial Data Warehouse
- Integrated planning tools
- Recommendations for spatial & transport strategies

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Figure 7 - HARMONY leaflet back

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HARMONY general presentation

Figure 8 - HARMONY general presentation – template of first slide

Figure 9 - HARMONY general presentation – content slide 1

Meet Our Team

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Figure 10 - HARMONY general presentation - content slide 2

Meet Our Team

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Figure 11 - HARMONY general presentation - content slide 3

HARMONY website

Figure 12 - HARMONY website - homepage

Figure 13 - HARMONY website - our vision

Our Solutions

Harmony will provide decision makers with a new generation of tools, policy recommendations and guidelines to lead the transition to the new mobility era. Our solutions will bridge the transport gap between metropolitan regions and neighbouring areas, working towards a resilient, sustainable, and intermodal transport system.

Our main solutions will be:

-

Model suite

It is a platform bringing together transport and spatial planning tools, people and freight activity-based models, network models and land use models. This integrated approach is necessary for authorities to understand if policies are sustainable, while also contribute to meeting COP23 targets, social equality and wellbeing. The Harmony model suite is also linked to an EU-wide model to analyse the impact of the concepts and technologies on the TSN/T level.
-

Training material and activities

Authorities and transport professionals will develop skills and knowledge to use the model suite tools. They will also provide advice for future projects and exploitation activities.
-

Best practices for SUMP's

The best practices for SUMP's will provide authorities with evidence-based recommendations to update their Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, including autonomous vehicles and drones.

Figure 14 - HARMONY website - our solutions

HARMONY newsletter

NEWSLETTER 1 - SEPTEMBER 2019,

A NEW MOBILITY ERA

Harmony is providing public authorities of metropolitan areas with the right tools to update their Sustainable Mobility Plans (SUMP) and lead the transition towards a new mobility era.

WHAT'S INSIDE THIS ISSUE:

- Our launch event* - 3
- Interview* - 4
- Upcoming events* - 5

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Figure 15 - HARMONY newsletter – example

HARMONY social media

Figure 16 - HARMONY LinkedIn homepage

Figure 17 - HARMONY Twitter homepage

Figure 18 - HARMONY YouTube homepage

HARMONY press release

Press Release

Logo of Partner

The European project “Harmony” was launched in London

Harmony envisages the development of a new generation of harmonised spatial and multimodal transport planning tools which comprehensively model the dynamics of the changing transport sector and spatial organisation, enabling metropolitan area authorities to lead the transition to a low carbon new mobility era in a sustainable manner.

Barcelona, 11th June 2019

Harmony is a European project funded by the European Commission within the programme Horizon 2020. Its name stands for “Holistic Approach for Providing Spatial & Transport Planning Tools and Evidence to Metropolitan and Regional Authorities to Lead a Sustainable Transition to a New Mobility Era”. Its consortium gathers 21 members from 9 different European countries that will be working together for the three and a half years to come.

Against the background of expanding urbanisation and evolving transport challenges, Harmony will support public authorities and service providers in transport and spatial planning. As such, Harmony will be cooperating with CIVITAS, a network of European cities committed to testing and implementing urban transport solutions for a more sustainable mobility.

More specifically, it will elaborate a model suite, i.e. a platform bringing together not only transport and spatial planning models but also regional community growth models. For example, it will address challenges related to land use, passenger and freight transport, multimodal mobility and so on. Consequently, these models will inform suitable recommendations to be implemented in different urban scenarios. Harmony will test its solutions in 6 different cities and metropolitan areas, namely Rotterdam - NL, Oxfordshire - UK, Athens - GR, Turin - IT, Trikala - GR, Katowice - POL. Real-life testing will include demonstrations with drones and autonomous vehicles at the service of citizens' needs. In addition, Harmony will provide a platform for multi-stakeholders' partnerships and appropriate training for public officials in order to close the gap between understanding and planning the mobility of the future.

The whole consortium gathered for the kick-off meeting at UCL in London, UK, on 5th and 6th June 2019. After a general overview of the project by the coordinator Dr Maria Kamargianni, each member of the consortium introduced its work package and explained its role within the project. Furthermore, the consortium had the pleasure of hosting the project officer from the European Commission, Dr Octavia Stepan, who underlined the meaningful impact Harmony will produce in addressing travelling demand and CO2 reduction at a regional level.

The meeting was followed by the public launch event on 7th June, with more than 150 participants registered. It was structured in three main panels of experts, each one focusing on a different aspect: innovation proposed by industries, challenged faced by urban authorities, spatial and transport planning. Finally, a cross-session discussion wrapped up the event and shed some light into future developments.

You can follow Harmony on [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#) to keep updated with its next developments.

Boiler plate: here you can describe your organization and the activities developed in the project (no more than 5-6 sentences - the complete press release should adjust to two pages)

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Figure 19 - HARMONY press release example

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815269

HARMONY videos

Figure 20 - Caption from video of HARMONY kick-off event

Figure 21 - Caption from video of HARMONY launch event

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[#harmony-h2020](https://twitter.com/Harmony_H2020)

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/harmony-h2020/>

For further information please visit www.harmony-h2020.eu